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Pd(0) nanoparticles immobilized on multinitrogen functionalized halloysite for promoting Sonogashira reaction: studying the role of the number of surface nitrogens in catalytic performance

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Abstract

Halloysite nanoclay, Hal, was amine-functionalized and subsequently reacted with 2,4,6-trichloro-1,3,5-triazine, TCT, and ethylenediamine, EDA, to provide multinitrogen containing functionality on the surface of Hal. The resulting surface-modified Hal, Hal-2N-TCT-EDA, was then used for immobilization of Pd nanoparticles and affording a heterogeneous catalyst, Pd@Hal-2N-TCT-EDA, with utility for copper and ligand-free Sonogashira coupling of alkynes and aryl halides. The results established the efficiency of this protocol in terms of product yield, ecofriendly nature, and reaction time. Study of the reusability of the catalyst confirmed that the catalyst could be recovered and recycled up to seven times with slight loss of catalytic activity and Pd leaching, indicating the efficiency of Hal-2N-TCT-EDA for embedding Pd nanoparticles. To elucidate the role of the number of surface nitrogens on the catalytic performance, the catalytic activity, and recyclability of the catalyst was compared with those of

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Hal-2N and Hal-2N-TCT. It was found that more surface nitrogen atoms gave higher loading of Pd and lower Pd leaching. This result confirms the contribution of surface nitrogens to anchor the Pd species and suppress leaching.

Keywords: Halloysite clay, functionality, Pd nanoparticles, copper and ligand-free, Sonogashira coupling reaction